

Distant Reading Textual AI Art Prompts

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The past months have seen a Cambrian explosion of high-quality neural image generation systems. They share the quite novel idea that users can enter textual prompts to inform the generation process according to their desired visual output. While early tools required a lot of technical expertise and the use of dedicated hardware, online services like DALL·E, Midjourney and Adobe Firefly have brought this cutting-edge technology to everyone, unlocking novel creative opportunities and allowing all kinds of people to express themselves artistically in an unparalleled visual quality.

But what and how did they express exactly in the advent of this new technology? Which subjects are popular, which artists' styles do users try to imitate, are they informed users of art-historical categories and vocabulary? How much of the prompts do genuinely originate from the user's own imagination and prompt engineering skills and how much is likely just copied from others?

Generative models for image synthesis have already been proposed in the DH as valuable means to "facilitate the exploration of the semantic structure of large image corpora" (Offert, 2020). The analysis of their widespread use "in the wild" through large collections of natural language prompts adds further layers to the understanding of many concepts in art.

For this poster we collected prompts from various sources¹ covering different diffusion models and prompting environments. Our dataset incorporates and thus surpasses in size recently published collections like the one Wang et al. (2023) provide. To anchor our analyses in the world of traditional art, we extracted artist's names from the comprehensive Getty's Union List of Artist Names as well as Wikidata and several web-published "AI Art Style Guides", shared by power users. From these sources we generate a structured representation of interrelated artists, styles, periods, and techniques allowing us to formally describe and compare the analyzed prompts. The goal is to uncover, document and evaluate presence, exchangeability and perceived stylistic surroundings of mentioned artists.

The prompts constitute a form of "natural language" expression but at the same time have the quality of simple "commands" to a computer system – seemingly unordered lists of short repetitive phrases. They are neither grammatically correct nor strictly governed by a closed set of words or phrases which complicates NLP and generally makes a deeper understanding of the semantics of prompt parts quite challenging. While short text topic models like (Yin and Wang, 2014) can be employed to capture the domain specific distributed semantics of individual words, there are specific measures to be taken in order to segment the prompts into coherent workable phrases and to extract boilerplate sections. Entity and feature recognition as well as phrase recognition must be customized, as detailed in the poster.

A graph-based analysis is then used to correlate the identified phrases with each other and to reveal clusters and interrelations. We consider co-occurrence and second-order co-occurrence (occurrence in similar contexts but not with each other) in order to highlight certain aspects of narrower and broader semantic relatedness. Ultimately, we aim to reliably identify similar prompts in the dataset that were part of a prompt engineering exploration process. From this we gain insights into the genesis of complex and increasingly sophisticated prompts and can infer the role of certain phrases for achieving specific visual goals. The image below shows a small portion of a cluster of interrelated prompts with their diverging passages:

highly detailed **long-shot** photo of a **long hair princess in the middle** of a baroque dreamy room full of renaissance furniture, cinematic lighting, intricate, 4k resolution, elegant

highly detailed **long-shot** photo of a **long hair princess walking in** a baroque dreamy room full of renaissance furniture, cinematic lighting, intricate, 4k resolution, elegant

highly detailed **long-shot** photo of a **unique long hair princess** in a baroque dreamy room full of renaissance furniture, cinematic lighting, intricate, 4k resolution, elegant

highly detailed **medium shot** photo of a **long flowery hair princess walking in** a baroque dreamy room full of renaissance furniture, cinematic lighting, intricate, 4k resolution, elegant

highly detailed photo of an **humanoid android walking in** a baroque dreamy room full of renaissance furniture, cinematic lighting, intricate, 4k resolution, elegant, **gold and purple**

This in-depth analysis is finally enriched by overlaying the graph with our list of artist's names. For the artists we ask several high-level questions: Are they mere "synonyms" for a certain style? Are they part of a boilerplate text, copied to enhance the overall artistic impression of the piece indiscriminately? Do they have the "correct" semantic surroundings regarding style, genre and motives, as art history would put them?

This contribution looks specifically into the emerging cultural technique of creating textual prompts, focusing mainly on text and network analysis. However, the readily available diffusion models such as Stable Diffusion (Rombach et al. 2021) lend themselves to experiments on image creation, therefore we also generate images in order to assess and communicate our findings.

This figure shows a collage from 12 images generated with the same seeds and parameters, only varying in one word. It shows a result of systematic experiments to validate the existence of (sometimes subtle) yet systematic stylistic effects of cohyponyms from identifiable clusters on the overall visual appearance.

Fußnoten

1. These include data sets from Kaggle, Github repositories as well as crawled data from pages like <https://lexica.art> and <https://krea.ai> – A full list will be given in the poster’s fine print.

Bibliographie

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